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Numerical Simulation of MILD combustion with adaptive finite rate chemistry

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MILD combustion

The Moderate or Intense Low oxygen Dilution (MILD) combustion:

- Preheated oxidizer stream
- Distributed reaction zone
- No visible flame

Advantages :

- High efficiency
- Low NO_x and CO emissions

$$Da = \frac{\text{turbulent timescale}}{\text{chemical timescale}} = \frac{\tau_T}{\tau_C}$$

Traditional flame

MILD combustion flame

(Parente et al., 2007)

Challenges of turbulent combustion simulation

Multi-scale (decades of scales) and **multi-physics** (fluid dynamics, chemical kinetics)

Prohibitive number of tightly coupled **equations** for real fuels and systems ($5 + N_{sp}$)

Turbulent combustion modelling approaches

Currently popular combustion models:

Model selected: EDC and PaSR

- Accuracy and cost are acceptable
- The distributed reaction zone of MILD combustion

Eddy Dissipation Concept can be coupled to finite rate chemistry

- Mean reaction rate

$$\bar{\omega}_k = -\frac{\bar{\rho}\gamma_\lambda^2}{\tau^*(1-\gamma_\lambda^3)} (\tilde{y}_k - y_k^*)$$

- Model parameters come from an energy cascade model
- Model constants

$$C_\gamma = 2.1377 \quad C_\tau = 0.4083$$

(Magnussen, 2005)

For MILD combustion :

$$C_\gamma = 1.9 \quad C_\tau = 1.47$$

(Parente et al., 2015)

Combustion takes place in the fine structure

- Combustion in the fine structures solved with two approaches

PSR: Perfectly Stirred Reactor

PFR: Plug Flow Reactor

Chemistry cost can be alleviated using mechanism reduction - Directed Relation Graph (DRG)

Source: Lu T and Law C.K. Proc. Combust. Inst., 30 (2005) 1333-1341

Species A depends on B, but B does not depend on A.

B and D are strongly related.

C depends on both B and D, but those links are weaker.

If A is the **target** species, then C can be removed without affecting the results of A.

Motivations and Objectives

• The **motivations** of this work focus on :

- Develop a modelling approach including **finite rate chemistry** for MILD combustion simulations;
- Understand the impacts of different **model parameters** on the results;
- Decrease the **calculation time** on finite rate chemistry.

• Thus, the **objectives** are:

- Use RANS simulation for **sensitivity analysis**;
- Implementation of DRG method to improve the **computational efficiency**;
- Conduct LES with EDC model which accounts for finite rate chemistry.

Experimental setup

Adelaide Jet-in-Hot-Coflow (JHC):

- Designed to emulate MILD combustion
- Fuel: methane/hydrogen mixture 50/50
- Secondary burner to provide hot combustion products to control O₂ level → dilution
- 3 streams : fuel jet, coflow, surrounding air
- Dilution level: 3% O₂
- Fuel-jet Reynolds number: 10,000
- Species mass fractions and temperature data are available

Simulation Setup

Reynolds Averaged Navier-Stokes (RANS)

Simulation:

- Mesh: 2D mesh with 30,000 cells
- Turbulent Model: k-epsilon model
- Chemistry model: Eddy Dissipation Concept
- Reactor type: PSR or PFR
- Transient solver edcPimpleSMOKE
- KEE mechanism on most cases
- DRG is used to save the computational time

Open FOAM

Sensitivity Analysis

- PFR vs. PSR
- k-epsilon model constant
- Multicomponent molecular diffusion
- EDC model coefficients
- Schmidt Number in species transport equation
- Mechanisms
- Boundary Conditions
- The impact of DRG

Sensitivity Analysis

- PFR vs. PSR

Temperature profiles using PFR and PSR reactors

Sensitivity Analysis

- EDC model coefficients

Standard: $C_\gamma = 2.1377$ $C_\tau = 0.4083$

Adjusted: $C_\gamma = 1.9$ $C_\tau = 1.47$

(Parente et al., 2016)

Effects of the adjustments of EDC constants on the Temperature profiles

Sensitivity Analysis

- Mechanisms (NOx free)

Mechanism Name	Number of Species	Number of Reactions
KEE (Bilger R. et al., 1990)	17	58
GRI3.0 (Gregory P. Smith et al., 1999)	36	219
SAN_DIEGO (University of California at San Diego, 2014)	50	247
POLIMI-HT (E. Ranzi et al., 2012)	84	1698

Comparison of Temperature profiles from different detailed chemistry mechanism

Sensitivity Analysis

- Boundary Conditions

Temperature profiles with uniform and non-uniform conditions

H2O mass fraction profiles with uniform and non-uniform conditions

CO mass fraction profiles with uniform and non-uniform conditions

Sensitivity Analysis

- The impact of DRG (with KEE mechanism)

Source: Lu T and Law C.K. Proc. Combust. Inst., 30 (2005) 1333-1341

Temperature profiles from the case with DRG turned off/on

2-3 times computational time saving with KEE mechanism

Preliminary Conclusions

• After the sensitivity analysis work:

- PSR and PFR reactors give similar simulation results ;
- Adjusted EDC constants aimed at MILD combustion help to reduce the over predicted temperature peak;
- Non-uniform boundary conditions improve the accuracy of downstream predictions;
- DRG helps to increase the computational efficiency by 2-3 times.

Extension of simulation from RANS to LES

- Mesh: 3D mesh with 1,500,000 cells
- **oneEqEddy** (k-equation eddy-viscosity model) turbulence model
- **Synthetic Turbulence (ST)** inflow generator and top-hat uniform mean velocity profile
- **Eddy Dissipation Concept** for turbulence/chemistry interactions
- **PFR** model for the fine structures
- One Step Chemistry

An overview of the LES mesh

LES mesh inlet regions

inletfuel

Transient and Mean Velocity Profiles

Temperature and Mixture Fraction Profiles

Mixture fraction along the center line

Prospects

- Based on the RANS case, the LES case needs further improvement;
- The case with ISAT (*In-situ* adaptive tabulation) combined with a reduced chemistry DRG (Directed Relation graph) will be conducted;
- PaSR model is expected to be included in the future work with LES;

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Thank you

Questions?

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